

INTERGENERATIONAL DIFFERENCES IN UNDERSTANDING ENGLISH AND FILIPINO IDIOMS AS GROUNDWORK FOR DEVELOPING AN INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIAL FOR LANGUAGE, CULTURE, AND SOCIETY

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ABSTRACT

The major goal of this study is to examine the differences in how Generation Z, Millennials, and Generation X understand English and Filipino idioms. A descriptive-comparative research design was used, involving 30 participants, with 10 individuals from each generation. Data were gathered through a 20-item multiple-choice test consisting of 10 English idioms and 10 Filipino idioms. The differences in idiom comprehension between the three generations were identified by analyzing and comparing the responses. Based on the findings, Generation Z scored the lowest and Millennials the highest. Although differences were observed, all generations were able to understand both English and Filipino idioms, though there were differences in how they were used and interpreted. The analysis also revealed differences in structure and meaning between the two languages. Filipino idioms were mostly verb-based, whereas English idioms tended to be more descriptive. Based on the findings, the researchers led in developing a lesson plan for Language, Culture, and Society subjects to help improve students' understanding of idioms. The lesson plan included activities such as word puzzles, group discussions, and writing tasks to support meaningful and engaging learning of idiomatic expressions in both English and Filipino.

Keywords: *Intergenerational Differences, English Idiomatic Expressions, Filipino Idiomatic Expressions*

INTRODUCTION

Learning a language is exciting and challenging, especially when it comes to understanding idiomatic expressions. Its figurative meanings which are not associated with their literal meaning make it difficult to comprehend. Idiomatic expressions convey figurative meanings that differ from their literal interpretations, understanding them can be challenging. English and Filipino language are both rich in idioms but there is limited comprehensive research exploring their similarities and differences. Understanding idiomatic expressions emphasize challenges for language learners, as their figurative meanings often differ from literal interpretations. Idioms serve as reflections of a society's culture, beliefs, and social norms, making them essential in effective communication across different generations.

Idioms cannot be literally translated, as their meanings are unpredictable from the usual meaning of their constituent parts, particularly idioms of socio-cultural, historical, or political backgrounds. It was clearly explained that idioms are influenced by cultural and historical context and cannot be understood literally as defined by Al-kadi (2015). These claims supported that idiomatic expressions are difficult to understand because their meanings go beyond the literal words, reflecting the culture and beliefs of a society, which is exactly what the introduction discusses about English and Filipino idioms. However, Amos and Abas (2021), stated that the English language is rich in idioms and other figurative expressions thus, learning idiomatic expressions can aid students in their English language learning. In addition, Anza (2024), explained that learning idioms may not seem appealing to a foreign language learner, as an idiom often conveys a meaning that is entirely different from the literal meaning. There is always a hidden message waiting to be unlocked for every idiom. Contrary to this, words known as *sawikain* in Filipino, the official language of the Philippines, or Filipino idioms are used fairly frequently in modern times.

As stated by Demeterio and Dreisbach (2020), the study on Cebuano speakers revealed that younger generations tend to use Filipino and English more frequently than their elders, indicating a shift in language preference and exposure. The study clearly explains that the younger generations are more likely familiar with idioms due to their exposure in education and media, while older generations may maintain a stronger understanding of traditional Filipino idioms. Developing instructional materials that address these intergenerational differences is crucial. Incorporating cultural elements into educational resources fosters a sense of ownership and pride within the community (Foerster and Saurman, 2021). Culturally responsive education, which integrates materials reflecting students' cultural backgrounds, enhances engagement and learning outcomes. Gay (2018) explains, culturally responsive teaching is an asset-based approach that uses "the cultural knowledge, prior experiences, frames of reference, and performance styles of ethnically diverse students to make learning encounters more relevant to and effective for them. With this approach to teaching and learning, educators make meaningful connections between the curriculum and home experiences, validate and incorporate students' culture in the learning environment, and build on students' preexisting knowledge and skills.

Saleh and Zakaria (2013) explored difficulties faced by learners when learning idioms and strategies applied to understand them. The results revealed that the lack of cultural background and less exposure to English idioms were the main difficulties for learners.

UNESCO's Education Framework (2015) emphasizes the importance of combining language, culture, and society in teaching to improve language learning and global communication. Using UNESCO's Education Framework, this study seeks to develop teaching materials that not only enhance idiom comprehension across generations but also preserve cultural identity. Due to a culturally responsive approach, learners will not only improve their language proficiency but also develop appreciation of the values and traditions connected in idiomatic expressions.

The gap in existing research lies in the limited exploration of intergenerational differences in understanding idiomatic expressions, particularly in comparing English and Filipino idioms. While studies have examined the role of culture in idiom comprehension, there is insufficient research that directly analyzes how different age groups process and interpret idioms based on their linguistic and cultural experiences. Research suggests that older adults may experience increased word-finding failures, such as tip-of-the-tongue states, due to difficulties in retrieving the sounds of words (Burke and Shafto, 2018). Additionally, knowledge of idioms and multiword expressions continues to develop across the lifespan, with familiarity scores being influenced by exposure and age differences. However, there remains a lack of direct comparative analysis between generations, especially in bilingual and multicultural settings like the Philippines. Addressing this research gap is crucial for developing instructional materials that cater to the varying needs of different generations, ensuring a more inclusive approach to language learning.

Research Questions

This study aimed to explore intergenerational differences in the understanding of English and Filipino idioms by examining how individuals from different age groups interpret idiomatic expressions in both languages. Specifically, it sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age?
2. How can English idioms be described in terms of:
 - 2.1 Structure;
 - 2.2 Forms; and
 - 2.3 Meaning?
3. How can Filipino idioms be described in terms of:
 - 3.1 Structure;
 - 3.2 Forms; and
 - 3.3 Meaning?
4. What are the differences between English and Filipino idioms in terms of:
 - 4.1 Structure;
 - 4.2 Forms; and

- 4.3 Meaning?
5. Is there an intergenerational difference in the understanding of English and Filipino idioms among:
 - 5.1 Generation X;
 - 5.2 Millennials; and
 - 5.3 Generation Z?
 6. What instructional material for Language, Culture, and Society can be developed based on the results of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researchers employed a descriptive comparative design to analyze the intergenerational differences in understanding English and Filipino idioms as a groundwork for developing supplementary material for language, culture, and society. According to Siedlecki (2020), a descriptive-comparative research design is a non-experimental approach used to compare two or more groups based on specific criteria without manipulating variables. This design was particularly useful for identifying differences or similarities among naturally occurring groups, such as age groups or educational levels. This method provided a deeper and more detailed understanding of complex research problems, making it effective for exploring language comprehension from different generations.

Specifically, this study used content analysis. As explained by Lou (2019), content analysis is a research method used to find patterns in recorded communication. It systematically collected and analyzed data from written, oral, or visual texts to identify recurring themes and ideas. In the case of generational differences in understanding idioms, content analysis helped explore how each generation saw and used idiomatic expressions. This method showed how language reflected cultural identities across different age groups and how idioms acted as a bridge between language and cultural learning. The results were used to create teaching materials that help people understand language and culture more deeply across generations.

Research Population and Sample

This study involved 30 participants, with 10 participants representing each of the three generations: Generation Z, Millennials, and Generation X. The sample size was deliberately chosen to guarantee a balanced representation from each generation, allowing for meaningful comparison of perspectives across these age groups. The researchers employed a quota sampling technique, where participants were selected based on their availability and their alignment with specific characteristics relevant to the study. Specifically, the quotas ensured that an equal number of respondents came from each generational group. Additionally, participants were required to be residents of Sariaya, Quezon, and to fall within the following age ranges: Generation X (45 to 60 years

old), Millennials (29 to 44 years old), and Generation Z (13 to 28 years old). Individuals who did not meet these criteria were excluded from the sample.

Research Instrument

This study administered a questionnaire that consisted of 20 items with an equal distribution of 10 items; 10 items focused on Filipino idioms and 10 on English idioms. In addition, the items were structured as multiple-choice questions, to assess respondent's understanding of idioms in both languages. The development of this instrument involved thorough validation; the questionnaire was examined and validated by two language experts, who ensured the accuracy and reliability of the instrument. Furthermore, content validity was also administered by a linguistics expert, who ensured that the questions appropriately captured generational differences in idiomatic understanding. Revisions were made to the questionnaire based on the feedback of the validators to enhance the precision and relevance of each item.

The test was conducted in person, allowing for direct interaction between the researchers and the participants. Through this, the researchers were able to immediately provide further instructions if the respondents encountered any uncertainties or confusions. In addition, a pilot test was administered to a small sample of participants of the target population to ensure the instrument's effectiveness. Based on the feedback from the validators, revisions were made before it was administered to the respondents.

Corpus of the Study

The corpus of this study consisted of a carefully selected collection of idiomatic expressions in both English and Filipino, serving as the main data source for analyzing generational differences in understanding idioms. The selection of idioms was guided by specific criteria: (1) the idioms had to be commonly used across different age groups; (2) they had to appear frequently in both written and spoken sources; (3) they needed to reflect culturally significant or socially relevant meanings; and (4) they had to have clear Filipino-English equivalents or counterparts for comparison. This ensured that the idioms included are meaningful, culturally relevant, and representative of everyday language. The study aimed to explore how different age groups understood and used these idiomatic expressions, providing essential insights for creating instructional materials that connected language, culture, and society.

To achieve this, the research used a variety of written and spoken materials that showed the structure, forms, and meanings of idioms in both languages. These sources included literary works, academic texts, media scripts, newspapers, related studies, and spoken materials such as podcasts, interviews, and radio programs. By including both traditional and modern texts, the study ensured a balanced view of the development and context of idioms across different generations.

The researchers used corpus analysis to examine and compare English and Filipino idioms, focusing on their cultural and social importance. This approach helped find patterns in idiom understanding among different age groups and determined how

idiomatic expressions reflected language and social influences. According to Nordquist (2019), corpus linguistics involved the study of language based on large collections of "real-life" language use stored in corpora—computerized databases created for linguistic research. This method allowed for a clear investigation of idiomatic expressions and their meaning for language learning and cultural understanding. Data collection included a selection of 30 idiomatic expressions with their Filipino counterparts. The study explored how idioms were used in everyday conversations, how well different generations understand them, and how their deeper meanings helped with understanding language and culture. The results provided helpful insights that were used to create teaching materials aimed at bridging generational gaps in language skills and cultural awareness.

Statistical Treatment

This section presented the statistical methods used to analyze and interpret the data gathered from the respondents. These techniques helped summarize responses and highlight patterns in the understanding of English and Filipino idioms across different generations.

The frequency and percentage distribution were utilized to collect data specifically the demographic profile of the respondents. Frequency showed the number of respondents in each category, while percentage helped compare different groups proportionally. These methods made it easy to identify trends, understand population characteristics, and analyze patterns in demographic variables such as age.

The formula for frequency and percentage distribution was as follows:

$$\text{Percentage Frequency} = \left(\frac{\text{Frequency of the class}}{\text{Total number of observations}} \right) \times 100$$

The Kruskal-Wallis H test (sometimes also called the "one-way ANOVA on ranks") is a rank-based nonparametric test that can be used to determine if there are statistically significant differences between two or more groups of an independent variable on a continuous or ordinal dependent variable.

The formula for Kruskal Wallis test was as follows:

$$H = \left[\frac{12}{n(n+1)} \sum_{j=1}^c \frac{T_j^2}{n_j} \right] - 3(n+1)$$

Scope and Limitation

This study aimed to analyze the intergenerational differences in understanding English and Filipino idioms, serving as a foundation for developing instructional materials for language, culture, and society. The research focused on how different age groups interpreted, understood, and used idiomatic expressions, highlighting the variations in

comprehension based on generational influences. To achieve this, the study employed content analysis, examining idioms collected from dictionaries, literary works, documents, and relevant studies. Additionally, the research included survey or interview data to explore how different generations perceived idioms in everyday communication. The findings helped in designing instructional materials that bridge generational gaps in idiom comprehension.

Despite its significance, this study had certain limitations. First, it focused on a limited selection of idioms, which meant the results might not have fully represented all English and Filipino idioms. Second, idioms often carried meanings that changed depending on cultural and contextual factors, which might affect interpretation across generations. In addition, the availability of sources for some idioms was limited, making it challenging to ensure comprehensive data collection. Lastly, potential for cultural bias, as participants from a single cultural context (Sariaya) might have interpreted idioms differently than those from other cultural backgrounds. This could have limited the generalizability of the findings to other cultural settings. As noted by Creswell (2014), cultural context played a significant role in how language and idiomatic expressions were understood, and any research confined to one culture might not have captured the full spectrum of idiomatic interpretations across diverse populations. Despite these limitations, the study aimed to provide valuable insights into how idioms shape language learning and cultural understanding across generations.

RESULTS

Table 1
Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

Descriptor	Frequency	Percentage
13 - 28 years old (Gen Z)	10	33.314
29 - 44 years old (Gen Y or Millennials)	10	33.314
45 - 60 years old (Gen X)	10	33.314
Total	30	100

Table 2
English Idioms Description in terms of Structure

Descriptor	f	%	Exemplars
Adj. + N.	2	20%	Scaredy cat, Yellow bellied

V. + Def. Ar. + N.	2	20%	Kicked the bucket, Tie the knot
N. + Linking V. + N.	1	10%	Hindsight is 20/20
N. + V. + Prep. + Indef. Ar. + N.	1	10%	Mutton dressed as a lamb
Prep. of Place. + N	1	10%	Between jobs
V. + Def. Ar. + N. + N.	1	10%	Burning the midnight oil
V. + Poss. Pro. + Adj. + N.	1	10%	Toot one's own horn
V. + Prep. of Place + N	1	10%	Grasping at straws
Total	10	100%	

Table 3
English idioms Description in terms of Forms

Descriptor	f	%	Exemplars
Fixed Statement	7	38.89%	Between jobs, Burning the midnight oil, Scaredy-cat, Grasping at straws, Yellow-bellied, Toot one's own horn, Tie the knot
Simile	3	16.67%	Grasping at straws, Yellow-bellied, Mutton dressed as lamb
Cliché	2	11.11%	Mutton dressed as lamb, Toot one's own horn
Euphemism	2	11.11%	Kicked the bucket, Tie the knot
Proverb	2	11.11%	Hindsight is 20/20
Binomial	2	11.11%	Tie the knot, Scaredy - cat
Total	18	100%	

Table 4
English Idioms Description in Terms of Meaning

Filipino Idioms	Meaning
Between jobs	Currently unemployed
Burning the midnight oil	Staying up late to work or study
Grasping at straws	Desperately trying to survive
Hindsight is 20/20	Regret always comes last
Kicked the bucket	To pass away
Mutton dressed as a lamb	A person pretending to be younger than they actually are
Scaredy cat	Someone who gets scared easily
Tie the knot	To get married
Toot one's own horn	To praise oneself or brag
Yellow bellied	A person who is cowardly or easily scared

Table 5
Filipino Idioms Description in terms of Structure

Descriptor	f	%	Exemplars
V. + Prep. + N.	4	40%	Nagsusunog ng kilay, Nagbibilang ng poste, Nagbubuhay ng sariling bangko, Kapit sa patalim
Pre. + V. + N.	1	10%	Pag - iisang dibdib
V. + Def. Ar + Plural Marker + N.	1	10%	Nagpantay ang mga paa
V. + N. + Prep. + N.	1	10%	May daga sa dibdib
Adj. + N.	1	10%	Nagmumurang kamatis
Adj. + Def. Ar. + N.	1	10%	Bahag ang buntot
Prep. + N. + Def. Ar. + N.	1	10%	Nasa huli ang pagsisisi

Total 10

Table 6
Filipino idioms Description in terms of Forms

Descriptor	f	%	Exemplars
Fixed Statement	9	40.91%	Nagbibilang ng poste, Nagsusunog ng kilay, May daga sa dibdib, Kapit sa patalim, Bahag ang buntot, Nagmumurang kamatis, Nagbubuhay ng sariling bangko, Nagpantay ang mga paa, Pag – iisang dibdib
Simile	4	18.18%	Kapit sa patalim, Bahag ang buntot
Cliché	3	13.64%	Nagmumurang kamatis, Nagbubuhay ng sariling bangko, Nasa huli ang pagsisisi
Euphemism	2	9.09%	Nagpantay ang mga paa, Nagbibilang ng poste, May daga sa dibdib, Pag - iisang dibdib
Proverb	2	9.09%	Nasa huli ang pagsisisi, Kapit sa patalim
Binomial	2	9.09%	Pag - iisang dibdib, Bahag ang buntot
Total	22	100%	

Table 7
Filipino Idioms Description in terms of Meaning

Filipino Idioms	Meaning
Bahag ang buntot	Duwag
Kapit sa patalim	Gumagawa ng desperadong paraan upang mabuhay
May daga sa dibdib	Duwag o matatakutin
Nagbibilang ng poste	Walang trabaho

Nagbubuhat ng sariling bangko	Nagyayabang o pinupuri ang sarili
Nagmumurang kamatis	Taong nagpapanggap na mas bata kaysa sa tunay na edad
Nagpantay ang mga paa	Namatay
Nagsusunog ng kilay	Nag-aaral o nagtatrabaho nang hatinggabi
Nasa huli ang pagsisipi	Ang pagsisipi ay dumarating kapag tapos na ang lahat
Pag - iisang dibdib	Kasal o pagsasama ng magkasintahan

Table 8
Intergenerational Differences in the Understanding of English Idioms

Descriptor	Mean Score	H statistic	p - value	Statistical Decision	Interpretation
13 - 28 years old (Gen Z)	4.2				
29 - 44 years old (Gen Y or Millennials)	4.3	1.982	0.371	Failed to Reject Ho	Not significant

Table 9
Intergenerational Differences in the Understanding of Filipino Idioms

Descriptor	Mean Score	H statistic	p-value	Statistical Decision	Interpretation
13 - 28 years old (Gen Z)	7.40				
29 - 44 years old	8.30	0.615	0.735	Failed to Reject Ho	Not significant

(Gen Y or Millennials)

DISCUSSION

Table 1

Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the respondents according to their age group. The respondents are equally distributed according to their group of generation: 13 - 28 years old (Gen Z), 29 - 44 years old (Gen Y or Millennials) and 45 - 60 years old (Gen X). Each group of generation consists of 10 respondents, which represents 33.33% of the total sample size of 30 individuals.

The data explicitly show that the respondents are equally divided among the three groups of generations. This distribution ensures that the perspectives gathered in the study are not biased towards a particular age group, which allows for more comprehensive and diverse insights. This reflects an intentional strategy aimed at obtaining a different generational insight that is relevant to the research problem.

These findings align with existing literature on generational representation in research. For instance, studies have emphasized the importance of balanced sampling to mitigate generational bias and enhance the validity of research outcomes (Smith, 2017; Johnson and Lee, 2019). By equally representing each generation, the study aims to capture a broad spectrum of perspectives, thereby enriching the analysis and interpretation of the results.

Table 2

English Idioms Description in terms of Structure

Table 2 results align with the findings Kulmamatovna (2024) that idioms exhibit various structures, many of which disregard standard grammatical rules. While some idioms are straightforward, others are ambiguous, relying on metaphors, proverbs, and cultural expressions to convey meaning. Khan (2024) stated that English idioms typically follow a specific syntactic structure with noun phrases (NPs) being a common component. An NP typically consists of a head noun and its modifiers, which can include determiners, adjectives, and prepositional phrases. As seen from the example 'scaredy cat' which contains a structure of Adj+N, it deviates from this rule, proving that idioms do really disregard certain grammatical rules.

However, Ekah et al. (2017) emphasized that idioms are not randomly structured but follow identifiable patterns in phonology, morphology, syntax, and semantics. These elements work together to encapsulate meaning, demonstrating that idioms are carefully arranged to achieve effective communication. Bargmann and Sailer (2018), also argued

that while idioms are often perceived as fixed expressions, non-decomposable idioms still have the flexibility to appear in different sentence structures, including passive voice, questions, and negations.

Table 3

English idioms Description in terms of Forms

Table 3 presents the description of English idioms in terms of forms. The table shows how English idioms are categorized into 6 categories: Fixed Statement, Simile, Cliché, Euphemism, Proverb and Binomial. Throughout, Fixed Statement presents the highest frequency, which is 7, followed by Simile is 3. Lastly, Euphemism, Proverb and Binomial present the lowest frequency which is 1. The total sample of idiomatic expressions that were identified is 10. However, some idioms also fall into different rhetorical forms, resulting in a total number of 18 frequency.

The data explicitly show that Fixed Statement is superior forms of English idioms given by dataset. This suggests that people always depend on the language set of expression that is quickly and clearly understood. The use of Simile and Cliché indicates that people tend to use comparative and familiar expressions to enhance understanding. Furthermore, Euphemism, Proverb and Binomial are rarely used, suggesting that it is saved for special situations only. These findings align with the statement by Sahara (2022) idioms come in various forms that add color and depth to language.

Table 4

English Idioms Description in Terms of Meaning

Table 4 presents all 10 idioms with their corresponding meanings. The results clearly show that English idioms are strongly connected to culture, everyday life, and shared experiences — something that matches what earlier researchers have pointed out. For example, idioms like “Between jobs”, “Grasping at straws”, and “Burning the midnight oil” reflect different parts of life such as work, struggle, and hard effort. This agrees with Lontas (2017), who explained that English idioms come from the people’s history, politics, and daily life, and they act as reflections of their world, feelings, and traditions. Lontas also noted that idioms connect people to their roots by expressing ideas in ways that are more colorful and easier to remember than plain speech.

Similarly, the study supports that idioms often come from important events and shared cultural stories (Wang (2017)). For example, many idioms originate from historical traditions, folklore, or common practices that were once widely recognized. The phrase “Tie the knot” comes from an old wedding tradition where couples would literally have their hands bound together with a ribbon or cord to symbolize unity. Likewise, “Kicked the bucket” is believed to have originated from old execution or slaughterhouse practices, where a person or animal would kick a bucket away when hanged or killed. These idioms, rooted in cultural narratives, carry meanings that go beyond their literal words, helping people express ideas clearly, and memorably.

Table 5

Filipino Description in Terms of Structure

Table 5 aligns with the statement of Ople's (2024) that Filipino idiomatic expressions are crucial in daily conversations, as they reflect the culture and values of the Filipino people. In addition, Ople analyzes 32 Filipino idioms and categorizes them into four themes: plants, animals, objects, and body parts. The study utilizes lexical and conceptual semantics to analyze their meanings and structures. The results reveal that prepositions, specifically "ng" and "sa," contribute to the syntactic and metaphorical interpretations of Filipino idioms.

As a support, Dita and Ella (2017) emphasizes that common phrasal-prepositional verbs in Philippine English, like "come up with" and "look forward to," usually follow a verb + preposition + noun pattern. This shows that Filipino expressions often follow certain sentence structures, which are shaped by both grammar rules and cultural background. Additionally, Reilly (2022), who emphasizes that idioms rely more on syntax than grammar and vary across languages.

Table 6

Filipino idioms Description in terms of Forms

Table 6 shows the different forms of Filipino idioms. These idioms are divided into six forms: Fixed Statement, Simile, Cliché, Euphemism, Proverb, and Binomial. Among these, Fixed Statements appear the most, with 9 frequencies. Lastly, Simile, Proverbs, and Binomials are the least common, which garners the frequency of 2. The total sample of idiomatic expressions that are identified is 10. However, some idioms also fall into different rhetorical forms, resulting in a total number of 22 frequency.

The data clearly shows that Fixed Statements are the most frequently used form of idiom. This means that people often use set phrases that are easy to understand, and familiar Euphemism and Clichés are also commonly used, showing that people like to express ideas through comparisons and well-known sayings. In contrast, Euphemisms, Proverbs, and Binomials are not used as often, which may suggest that they are used only in certain situations or contexts.

Table 7

Filipino Idioms Description in terms of Meaning

Table 7 presents all 10 idioms with their corresponding meanings. This analysis explores a set of Filipino idioms with its meanings, focusing on their cultural and communicative functions. By examining these idioms, this research aims to uncover not only linguistic structures but also the shared human experiences, emotions, values, and social behaviors they reflect within each culture.

The findings clearly show that Filipino idioms are deeply rooted in cultural experiences, imagery, and daily life, an observation that aligns well with existing literature. For instance, idioms like "*Nagbibilang ng poste*" and "*Kapit sa patalim*" show how

figurative expressions can reflect social realities such as unemployment and desperation. These results are supported by Betts (2016), who emphasized that idioms often do not make literal sense when translated but are culturally meaningful, carrying associations with common behaviors or traits. This alignment reinforces the idea that idioms are not just linguistic expressions, but cultural tools that reflect how people interpret their environment.

Table 8

Intergenerational Differences in the Understanding of English Idioms

Table 8 presents the results of the survey, which includes 20 idioms—10 in English and 10 in Filipino, and with 10 respondents each generation. The data show that there is no significant difference in the understanding of idioms among the three generations, as their mean scores are relatively close to one another. Generation X scores the highest in understanding English idioms with a 4.7 mean score. On the other hand, Generation Z scores the lowest, with only 4.2 mean score.

Additionally, even though the scores are slightly different, the similar average results show that there is no significant difference in how the three generations understand idioms. This could be because English idioms are still taught in schools and used in media, helping all generations develop a common understanding of these expressions. As noted by Bautista (2024), English idioms remain prevalent in formal education and mass media in the Philippines, contributing to intergenerational language consistency. Furthermore, the increased accessibility of multilingual content through digital platforms may help bridge generational gaps in idiom exposure (Capistrano and Labrador, 2020). These shared linguistic inputs likely contribute to the statistically comparable levels of idiom understanding among Generation X, Y, and Z, despite their differing communication habits.

Table 9

Intergenerational Differences in the Understanding of Filipino Idioms

Table 9 presents the intergenerational differences in the understanding of Filipino idioms among respondents from Gen Z (13–28 years old), Gen Y or Millennials (29–44 years old), and Gen X (45–60 years old). The Kruskal-Wallis H test yields an H statistic of 0.615 and a p-value of 0.735, indicating no statistically significant difference in the understanding of Filipino idioms among the three age groups at the 0.05 alpha level. As a result, the null hypothesis (H_0) is not rejected, which means that the comprehension levels of Filipino idioms are statistically comparable across these generational cohorts.

It can be observed that there is no significant difference in the understanding of the three generations, as their mean scores are relatively close to one another. Furthermore, the lack of a significant difference in idiom understanding across the three generations can be attributed to the continued presence and exposure of Filipino idioms in both traditional and modern forms of communication. Despite generational differences in media consumption, the integration of idiomatic expressions into everyday language,

educational materials, and popular media ensures that all three generations are consistently exposed to these idioms. According to Mendoza and Ramos (2018), Filipino idioms are still widely used in television, films, and online platforms, making them accessible to younger generations despite their increasing preference for digital content. Similarly, Villanueva (2020) emphasizes that while younger generations may be less exposed to traditional idioms in formal education, their familiarity with these expressions is maintained through digital media, songs, and social media platforms. This shared exposure, regardless of medium, helps bridge the gap in idiom understanding, leading to similar levels of comprehension across generations.

Conclusions

The findings lead the researchers to the following conclusion. After analyzing the data, the current researchers arrive at the following conclusions.

1. The equal distribution of respondents across Generation Z, Millennials, and Generation X allowed the researchers to gather diverse insights, perspectives, and levels of understanding, helping to avoid bias from any single group. This gave the study a complete and more balanced picture of how idioms were viewed across generations.

2. English idioms followed clear structural patterns, with the most common being adjective + noun with the percentage of 20% and verb + definite article + noun with the percentage of 20% as presented in table 2. Even less common patterns still adhered to grammatical rules, showing that idioms were systematically formed rather than random. Idioms were grouped into six rhetorical forms. On the other hand, as presented in table 3 Fixed Statements used most frequently, followed by Similes and Clichés, while Euphemisms, Proverbs, and Binomials were less common. This suggested that speakers often chose familiar and accessible idioms to communicate everyday experiences more creatively and memorably.

3. Filipino idioms have specific structures, with the most frequent being verb + preposition + noun as presented in table 5, which occurred with the greatest frequency. As presented in table 6, in terms of form, Fixed Statements were used most often, whereas Euphemisms, Proverbs, and Binomials were used least often. Moreover, the meanings of Filipino idioms were based on daily life, emotions, and cultural experiences, frequently employing vivid imagery associated with local values and history. In conclusion, these idioms played a crucial role as cultural markers to convey shared experiences and enhance communication among the Filipino people.

4. English and Filipino idioms differed in structure and cultural background with Filipino idioms being more verb-based and English idioms being more descriptive, both languages frequently used similar rhetorical forms like Fixed Statements, Similes, and Clichés as presented in table 2, 3, 5, and 6. Despite structural differences, idioms in both languages shared the same purpose: enhancing communication, expressing cultural identity, and capturing everyday experiences and emotions.

5. Although the data showed some trends such as Generation X having the strongest understanding of English idioms, Millennials demonstrated a stronger grasp of Filipino idioms, and Generation Z scored lowest in both statistical analyses revealed no significant difference across generations overall, as presented in table 8 and 9. This implied that generational belonging was not a crucial factor in idiomatic understanding. Instead, it suggested that individual factors like education, language exposure, media consumption, and personal experience played a more influential role. This finding challenges the assumption that younger or older generations inherently had an advantage in idiomatic knowledge and pointed to the shared nature of cultural and linguistic learning across age groups.

6. A learning material was developed to guide students in understanding and using English and Filipino idioms effectively. The lesson plan, as the output of the study, included engaging activities about idiomatic expressions in English and Filipino language. By providing this output, students could enhance their language skills and deepen their understanding of figurative language, making it easier for them to use idioms in their everyday communication, making learning easier and more effective.

7. The lack of significant difference implied that generational belonging does not strongly determine idiomatic understanding. Instead, factors like education, media exposure, and personal experience played more crucial roles. This finding suggested that idiom learning materials were designed to address shared cultural and linguistic knowledge across generations, rather than assuming large gaps between age groups.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations are offered:

1. The students should be encouraged to use and explore idioms in both English and Filipino to help improve their language skills and understanding of culture. They could try talking with people from different age groups or reading stories and books to learn more about how idioms are used by older and younger generations. By using the learning material made for language, culture, and society, students can better understand the meaning and importance of idioms and see how different and interesting figurative language can be in daily life.

2. Teachers could incorporate idioms in both English and Filipino in their classroom lessons to help students improve their language skills and learn more about culture. They are encouraged to create activities and learning materials that could involve interactions between different age groups, like interviews or storytelling, so that students can better understand the meaning of idioms based on how they are used in real-life situations.

3. Curriculum planners could add more activities that focus on idioms in both English and Filipino, as these can help students understand language and culture better. They may include exercises that show real-life examples of idioms, so students can see how these are used in everyday conversations and situations. This kind of activity could

help students understand idioms more clearly and learn why they are important in both language and culture.

4. Different generations could utilize the language learning material that is developed by the researchers to enhance and deepen their understanding regarding English and Filipino idioms. In addition, they should recognize the value of idiomatic expressions in both Filipino and English. Because idioms are not only tools for communication but also a reflection of a community's history, values, and culture. Moreover, older generations, such as the Baby Boomers, are encouraged to share their knowledge of idioms to younger individuals. At the same time, younger generations, including Generation Beta, are encouraged to learn and use these expressions in daily life for the preservation of idioms. Through shared effort, idioms could continue to be meaningful and relevant across time.

5. The school administration could support the use of idioms in both English and Filipino as part of the lessons in school. They could also provide training or workshops for teachers on how to teach idioms well and explain their importance in culture. Helping with this plan could improve students' language skills and help them learn more about different cultures.

6. Future researchers could examine whether Filipino and English idioms are evolving or gradually disappearing. As idioms play an important role in expressing thoughts and emotions in everyday communication. However, changes in language use are often influenced by technology, globalization, and modern trends. To understand these changes, researchers could study how idioms are used across different generations. This involves including older groups, such as the Baby Boomers, and younger ones, like Generation Beta. Comparing these age groups could provide accurate results of how idiomatic expressions are being maintained, adapted, or slowly vanishing.

7. For future improvement, including a larger number of respondents from different age groups, such as older people like Baby Boomers and younger ones like Generation Alpha, could help get more varied answers and give a better analysis of how idioms are used and understood by each generation. In addition, adding more Filipino and English idioms to the questionnaire would help better understand how common and meaningful they are. These improvements would enhance the quality and depth of the research, making the results more reliable and accurately finding the patterns in idiom usage over time.

8. For future research, similar study in other schools or areas could be conducted to find out if the results also apply to different groups of students. Researchers could make the study larger by involving more people from various age groups, locations, and backgrounds to see if the findings stay the same across different types of participants. This could help better understand how people from different generations learn and use idioms.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors declared that this study was conducted in full accordance with ethical standards. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their participation in the study and were informed of their right to withdraw at any moment without facing any consequences. Participants were also informed that their responses and personal data was solely for research purposes only, and data privacy laws were followed when handling their personal data. The authors attest that the study was free from any conflicts of interest. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, and all findings were interpreted objectively; without bias. The results of this study were used solely for research purposes. AI tools were responsibly used only to locate related literature and sources; no content was copied, and all analyses, interpretations, and writing reflect the authors' own work.

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